

Use of Copper(III) Periodate and Copper(III) Tellurate as Oxidants : Oxidative Decarboxylation of α -Hydroxy Acids

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Manuscript received 24 September 1993, accepted 16 November 1993

The chemistry of Cu^{III} compounds is becoming very attractive and oxidation of organic substrates by $[\text{Cu}(\text{HIO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ has received considerable attention¹. Representative examples illustrate mainly the mechanism and kinetics of oxidation of primary α -alcohols^{2,3}, aldehydes^{4,5}, ketones⁶, aliphatic amines⁷ and carboxylic acids⁸. The Cu^{III} -peptide complexes has been shown to effect the decarboxylation of glyoxalate ion in basic medium⁹.

With a view to studying the applicability of Cu^{III} periodate (or tellurate) as oxidant in synthetic organic chemistry, the following investigations were carried out although Movius² predicted that such reagent would not be attractive oxidant. It has been observed that under alkaline condition these reagents can effect oxidative decarboxylation of certain α -hydroxy acids (1) to the respective carbonyl compounds (2).

Benzilic acid (1; X = Y = C_6H_5) was selected as the pilot compound to establish the optimum condition for the oxidation.

Thus the reaction of benzilic acid in dilute sodium hydroxide solution with Cu^{III} -periodate or -tellurate furnished benzophenone in 95% yield. In this procedure, 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene (1; X-Y = C_6H_4 - C_6H_4), mandelic and citric acids were oxidised. The carbonyl compounds were iden-

tified through the respective 2,4-DNP derivatives. It was found that the yields of the desired products were better with aromatic substrates than those with aliphatic compounds.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Each experiment was repeated several times. Ir spectra were taken in Perkin-Elmer 177 and 297 spectrophotometers. Double-distilled water, prepared by boiling over KMnO_4 , was used throughout.

*Cu^{III}-periodate*¹⁰ : To the stirred solution of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (12.5 g) in double-distilled water (900 ml), were added KIO_4 (57.5 g) and KOH (67.5 g, dissolved in minimum volume of water) when a deep green solution resulted. Potassium persulphate (60.0 g) was then added to it and the mixture boiled for 15–20 min. The resulting deep brown solution was diluted with water to 1 dm³ and stored in a polythene container. Alternatively, the solution could be evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath from a porcelain basin and the brown residue powdered and stored. The reagent was diluted with calculated amount of water just before use.

*Cu^{III}-tellurate*¹⁰ was also prepared by the aforementioned method.

Oxidation of benzilic acid : To a solution of benzilic acid (0.5 g) in 4 N NaOH (10 ml) was added Cu^{III} -periodate (30 ml) with shaking. The reaction mixture was warmed on a steam-bath for 2–3 min when the deep brown solution abruptly changed to green. The reaction

mixture was then cooled and acidified (congo red) with 6*N* HCl and extracted (3 × 25 ml) with a mixture of ether and benzene (1 : 1, v/v). The combined organic phase was washed successively with water (3 × 20 ml), saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (3 × 20 ml; preserved), finally with water (3 × 20 ml) and dried (Na₂SO₄). On removal of the solvent a colourless oily residue was obtained (0.4 g), which furnished an orange-yellow 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 235°. The crude ketone was purified by evaporative distillation at 120–125°/12 mm to furnish colourless crystals (0.38 g, 95%), m.p. 48°, which remained undepressed on admixture with authentic benzophenone¹¹. The ir spectra of the product and that of the authentic benzophenone were identical in all respects¹² : ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 980, 1 925, 1 800, 1 645, 1 595, 1 575, 1 445, 1 320, 1 275, 1 175, 1 150, 1 075, 1 030, 1 000, 995, 945, 935, 915, 820, 765, 705, 695 and 640 cm⁻¹.

The preserved alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with concentrated HCl and worked up with ether in the usual way to yield colourless crystals (*ca* 10 mg) m.p. 147–48°, which remained undepressed on admixture with starting material. Cu^{III}-tellurate under identical condition oxidised benzoic acid to furnish benzophenone in 90% yield and traces of starting material was recovered.

Oxidation of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene : A mixture of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene (0.5 g), 4 *N* NaOH (10 ml) and Cu^{III}-periodate (40 ml) was stirred and warmed on a steam-bath for 2–3 min, when colour of the solution changed from deep brown to green. The cooled reaction mixture on workup with ether in the usual way furnished a neutral product (0.4 g) which was purified by evaporative distillation at 120°/12 mm to furnish pure fluorenone as pale yellow needles (0.36 g, 91%), m.p. 81°, m.m.p. with authentic sample remained undepressed. It furnished the 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 280–283°d. The ir spectra of the product and that of authentic fluorenone were identical in all respects¹² : ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 950, 1 925, 1 830, 1 715, 1 610, 1 595, 1 445, 1 370, 1 295, 1 195, 1 095, 1 080, 950, 915, 880, 810, 780, 730, 665 and 645 cm⁻¹.

Oxidation of mandelic acid : A mixture of mandelic acid (1.0 g), 4 *N* NaOH (20 ml) and Cu^{III}-periodate or -tellurate (60 ml) was heated on a steam-bath with occasional shaking for 2–3 min. The cooled green reaction mixture on similar workup with a mixture of ether and benzene (1 : 1, v/v) gave an oily material (0.4 g, 50%). It furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 233–35°, which remained undepressed on admixture with the authentic 2,4-DNP derivative of benzaldehyde.

The preserved alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with concentrated HCl and usual workup with ether-benzene mixture gave colourless solid (0.4 g, 50%), m.p. 120°, which remained undepressed on admixture with authentic benzoic acid.

Oxidation of citric acid : A mixture of citric acid (1.0 g), 4 *N* NaOH (30 ml) and Cu^{III}-periodate or -tellurate (90 ml) was warmed on a steam-bath for 2–3 min, then distilled to give acetone in 10% yield, which was identified and estimated through the 2,4-DNP derivative and iodoform. Other products could not be isolated.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. R. G. Bhattacharyya, Head, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University. One of the authors thanks Swami Suparnananda, Principal, R. K. M. R. College, Narendrapur, for encouragement.

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NOTE

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